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Effects of Kitchen Waste Compost on Soil CO₂-C Emissions, Microbial Properties, Enzyme Activity and Aggregate Fractions

Mubshra Naseer

Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, University of Turin, Turin 10100, Italy

Adil Nawaz

Institute of Agronomy, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan

Adila Iram

Ayub Agricultural Research Institute, Faisalabad

Aeysha Wishal*

Agronomy (Forage Production) Section, Ayub Agricultural Research Institute, Faisalabad Email: aeyshawishal@gmail.com

Kinza Waheed

Department of Biotechnology, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur

Muhammad Sajid*

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad 38040, Pakistan
Email: saajiduaf@gmail.com

Umair Gull

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad 38040, Pakistan

Muhammad Sajjad

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad 38040, Pakistan

Amina Rashid

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad 38040, Pakistan

Muhammad Muneeb Hassan

Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad 38040, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Graphical Abstract

Abstract

This study evaluated the effect of composted kitchen waste on soil CO₂-C emissions, microbial biomass, enzyme activity, and aggregate stability. A 75-day laboratory incubation experiment was conducted at 20 °C at the University of Agriculture Faisalabad. The experiment consisted of five treatments including fresh banana peel, fresh potato peel, banana peel compost, potato peel compost, and a control (soil without amendment), arranged in a completely randomized design (CRD). Cumulative CO₂-C emissions were highest in potato peel (597 mg C kg⁻¹ soil) and potato compost (542 mg C kg⁻¹ soil), indicating rapid decomposition, with generally higher emissions from fresh residues than composts. Microbial biomass carbon (MBC) was highest in banana peel (1056 mg C kg⁻¹ soil) and potato compost (983 mg C kg⁻¹ soil). Enzyme responses varied among treatments, with β-glucosidase higher in fresh residues, chitinase enhanced under potato compost, and leucine aminopeptidase highest in banana peel, reflecting substrate-specific microbial activity. Aggregate formation was also treatment-dependent, with greater macroaggregate formation observed under fresh banana peel compared to composts. These findings indicate that fresh residues stimulate higher CO₂-C emissions and aggregation, while composts enhance microbial biomass and selectively influence enzyme activities, contributing to soil functional improvement.

Keywords: Organic Kitchen Waste, Soil Respiration, Microbial Activity, Extracellular Enzymes, Soil Incubation, Soil Aggregates

Abbreviation: Dissolved organic carbon (DOC), Soil organic carbon (SOC), Microbial biomass carbon (MBC), Complete randomized design (CRD), Electrical conductivity (EC), Greenhouse gases (GHGs)

Introduction

In developing countries, rapid urbanization and population growth have increased municipal solid waste production, contributing significantly to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Global food demand has increased with economic development and population growth, leading to higher kitchen waste generation, which constitutes a major fraction of municipal solid waste (Hafid et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2019). Worldwide, more than 38 billion m³ of organic solid waste is generated from humans, livestock, and agricultural activities (Diacono et al., 2019). Kitchen waste constitutes a major fraction of municipal solid waste, which depends on the eating habits of the consumers (Liu et al., 2019). People generate kitchen waste such as vegetable offal, leftovers, and fruit peels as a result of both industrial and domestic activities. Kitchen waste is highly heterogeneous, with moisture content ranging from 74–90%, volatile solids constituting 80–97% of total solids, and a C:N ratio of 14.7–36.4% (Cerda et al., 2018), making it prone to rapid decomposition and potential environmental hazards. The perishable and heterogeneous nature of kitchen waste promotes leachate and gas production and pathogen enrichment, posing risks to human health and the environment (Yang et al., 2019).

Climate change is a major global challenge largely driven by greenhouse gas emissions from various anthropogenic activities, including the decomposition and management of organic wastes (Ahmed, 2020). The decomposition of organic wastes, including kitchen residues, contributes to greenhouse gas emissions such as CO₂ and CH₄, which play a role in global climate change (Kumar et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022). Soil organic matter (SOM) and organic carbon (SOC) are key for soil health (Ahmed et al., 2023).

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a critical component of the global carbon cycle, influencing soil fertility, plant productivity, and climate regulation (Kumawat et al., 2022). These processes regulate CO₂-C emissions and carbon stabilization in soil. (Loisel et al., 2019; Kelly et al., 2022).

Composting, an aerobic decomposition process, is widely used to recycle kitchen waste into stable organic amendments suitable for agricultural soils. Due to the presence of high moisture content, low pH, and low carbon to nitrogen ratio in kitchen waste, it is very difficult to incinerate kitchen waste (Sajid et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2022). So, composting is considered as an effective and sustainable method for converting kitchen waste into stabilized organic amendment for agricultural lands (Cerda et al., 2018). Organic substrates influence microbial respiration and C mineralization, including sugars, lipids, and proteins, which are progressively converted into more stable products like humic acids, fulvic acids, and Humin (Yang and Antonietti, 2020). Stable organic molecules have a good impact on soil quality, plant development, and plant health (Epelde et al., 2018). Recycling organic waste is increasingly important to restore soil nutrients and maintain soil health under intensive fertilization. Recycling organic waste for plant nutrient supply is becoming significantly more important for restoring plant nutrients, maintaining soil health, and controlling pollution. (Chatterjee et al., 2017). Despite the recognized importance of organic waste recycling, the form in which residues are applied fresh or composted can strongly influence decomposition dynamics, microbial activity, and soil structural

development. The form of residue application (fresh vs composted) strongly affects soil carbon dynamics and microbial processes. Limited studies compare fresh residues with their composted forms. Fresh materials may increase CO₂-C emissions, while composts may enhance microbial biomass and aggregation. Most studies assess these processes separately rather than together. Fresh residues typically undergo rapid decomposition and may stimulate higher microbial respiration and CO₂-C release, whereas composted materials represent more stabilized organic inputs that may influence microbial activity and soil aggregation differently. Furthermore, most previous studies evaluate these processes individually rather than examining carbon mineralization, microbial biomass, enzyme activity, and soil aggregation simultaneously. Therefore, controlled incubation studies comparing fresh and composted kitchen residues are necessary to better understand their differential effects on soil carbon dynamics and microbial functioning. Banana and potato peels were selected due to contrasting composition (sugar-rich vs starch-rich), which may differently influence decomposition and microbial activity. It is hypothesized that fresh residues increase CO₂-C emissions, while composts enhance microbial biomass, enzyme activity, and soil aggregation. The study aimed to: (i) compare the effects of fresh versus composted fruit and vegetable peels on soil CO₂-C mineralization, (ii) evaluate impacts on microbial biomass and enzyme activities, and (iii) assess changes in soil aggregation during incubation.

Materials and methods

Collection and preparation of soil samples

The experiment was conducted in the Soil and Bio-Geochemistry Laboratory of the Institute of Soil and Environmental Sciences, University of Agriculture Faisalabad. Soil samples were collected from the topsoil layer (0–15 cm) of the research farm of the Institute. From the experimental plot, five random cores were taken and composited to obtain a representative bulk sample. The collected soil was air-dried at room temperature (~25°C) for 48 hours, gently ground using a wooden pestle and mortar to break large aggregates, and then sieved through a 2 mm mesh to remove plant residues and gravels. Soil aggregate size distribution was determined using the wet-sieving method following standard aggregate fractionation procedures. The processed soil was stored at room temperature for 2 days before pre-incubation. Baseline soil analyses were performed on subsamples of this composited soil. For pH and electrical conductivity (EC) determination, soil saturated paste was prepared, and pH was measured using a calibrated pH meter while EC of the extract was measured using a digital conductivity meter. Soil chemical properties, including carbonates, bicarbonates, chlorides, calcium + magnesium, sodium, potassium, available phosphorus, and nitrogen, were determined following standard titration, flame photometry, spectrophotometry, and Kjeldahl methods. Soil physical parameters such as saturation percentage, water holding capacity, and texture were determined using gravimetric and hydrometer methods (Bouyoucos, 1962; Hesse, 1971). The initial soil moisture content was recorded as part of baseline characterization. Detailed physical and chemical properties of the soil used in the incubation experiment are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Physical and chemical characteristics of the soil used in incubation experiment

Collection and processing of banana and potato peels

Approximately 2 kg of each type of peel was used as feedstock for composting from fruits shops and each treatment was incubated in 500 mL glass jars containing 100 g of air-dried soil. Jars were loosely capped to allow gas exchange while minimizing

Soil Characteristics	Units	Values
Sand	%	40
Silt	%	38
Clay	%	22
Textural class	-	Loam
SP	%	33.86
pH _s	-	7.8
EC _e	dS m ⁻¹	1.5
CO ₃ ²⁻	me L ⁻¹	0.72
HCO ₃ ⁻	me L ⁻¹	8.2
Cl ⁻	me L ⁻¹	4.8
Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺	me L ⁻¹	0.556
Soil organic Matter	%	0.87

moisture loss, and positions were randomized to avoid positional effects. To allow natural air circulation, the glass jars were modified by creating perforations to allow aeration. Temperature, moisture, and odor were monitored weekly to track composting progress. The compost was turned every 6 days to maintain aeration and homogeneity throughout the 10-week period. Compost maturity was assessed based on stable temperature near ambient, dark brown color, earthy odor, and a

C:N ratio below 20. After maturity, the compost was air-dried, powdered, sieved (2 mm), and stored at room temperature for further use in the incubation experiment. The reaction mixture was incubated at 25°C for 1 hour in the dark to allow enzymatic hydrolysis of the fluorogenic substrates. The peels were washed with tap water to remove debris to remove any unwanted debris. The peels were cleaned and cut into small pieces (1-5 cm) before being air dried in the sun for 20 days. The dried peels were powdered, sieved (2 mm) and kept at room temperature for further use. All amendments were applied on a dry-mass basis (g per kg of soil). Amendment rates were standardized by total dry weight, not by carbon content. Differences in carbon input among treatments should be considered when comparing CO₂-C release. In addition, banana and potato peels characteristics are described in Table 2.

Table 2 Physical and chemical characteristics of compost and peels used in incubation experiment

Soil physical properties

Soil Saturation Percentage

Gravimetric method was used to determine the saturation percentage of soil. Two-

Characteristics	Units	Banana Compost	Banana peels	Potato compost	Potato peels
pH	-	7.5±0.23	9.5±0.1	9.2±0.1	6.9±0.1
EC	dS m ⁻¹	3.14±0.12	5.6±0.6	2.55±0.34	7.2±0.4
Total P	mg kg ⁻¹	0.3±0.1	0.3±0.1	0.4±0.05	0.33±0.1
Total K	mg kg ⁻¹	11.33±0.6	12±5.2	11.7±3.1	11±5.3
Total N	%	0.5±0.02	0.6±0.3	0.7±0.3	0.9±0.2
Carbon	%	27.4±2	27.5±2.1	26.9±1.3	28±0.9

hundred and fifty grams of soil was taken in a 200 mL beaker. First of all, soil saturated paste was prepared by using distilled water and following saturation paste criteria having no standing water, paste showing slight glistening and no free water. At first empty china dish weight was recorded, then the weight of soil saturated paste was recorded in china dish and soil paste was oven dried to obtain constant weight at 105 °C. Then, oven dried soil paste was weighed again. Saturation % of soil was calculated by following formula:

$$\text{Saturation (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Weight of saturated soil} - \text{Weight of oven-dried soil})}{(\text{Weight of oven dried soil})} \times 100$$

Water holding capacity of soil

As elaborated in manual ICARDA third edition, that WHC is half of the soil saturation %. So,

$$\text{Water holding capacity} = \frac{\text{Saturation percentage}}{2}$$

Soil particle distribution (Soil texture)

Soil particles analysis was done by Hydrometer method proposed by (Bouyoucos 1962). For the soil texture determination, soil is dispersed in 250 mL distilled water, dispersion solution was prepared by dissolving 2.5 g sodium carbonate and 10 g sodium hexametaphosphate. About 40 g of air-dried soil was taken in 600 ml beaker and addition of (60 mL) dispersion suspension was done. Watch glass was used to cover the solution and the mixture was left overnight. Next day, solution was transferred to stirring cup and stirred for 3 minutes after this material was transferred to 1 L graduated cylinder. When homogenous mixture was made reading was taken after forty seconds then after two hours by inserting hydrometer in the suspension. Temperature of hydrometer was maintained at 20 °C.

The quantity (%) of sand, silt and clay was determined as follows

$$\text{Clay (\%)} = \frac{\text{CHRC}}{(\text{Weight of Soil})} \times 100$$

$$\text{Silt + Clay (\%)} = \frac{\text{CHRsc}}{(\text{Weight of Soil})} \times 100$$

$$\text{Silt (\%)} = (\text{Silt + Clay}) - \text{Clay}$$

$$\text{Sand (\%)} = 100 - (\text{Silt + Clay})$$

CHRC = Reading of Hydrometer for clay

CHRsc = Reading of Hydrometer for Silt +clay

Chemical properties of Soil

pH of saturated soil paste (pHs)

For determination of soil pH, HANNA Model HI9811-5 pH meter was used. First, pH meter was standardized by using buffer solutions having pH values of 4, 7 and 10. After the calibration, probe of pH meter was dipped in saturated paste already prepared and stable reading was recorded (U.S. Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954; Method 21a).

Soil saturated extract

To obtain extract of soil saturated paste positive pressure was exerted with the aid of air pumping. Soil extract was stored in airtight bottles for further analysis (Wang et al., 2023).

Determination of electrical conductivity

For determining ECe of soil extract was taken by filtering through filter paper. First, digital portable conductivity meter (HANNA Model HI9811-5) was calibrated by

dipping probe in 0.01 N KCl solution and reading was noted. Cell constant and actual EC value were determined by below formulas:

$$\text{Cell constant (Kc)} = K = \frac{\text{Standard EC}}{\text{Observed EC}}$$

$$\text{Actual ECe (dS m}^{-1}\text{)} = Kc \times \text{Observed EC}$$

Soluble Cations

Calcium + Magnesium (Ca+Mg)

About 5 mL of soil extract was taken and diluted 5 times in beaker, then 10 to 15 drops of buffer solution and 2 to 3 drops of Erichrome Black-T (EBT) indicator were added. Then $\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}$ (me L^{-1}) were determined by titration with 0.01 N EDTA solution which changes the colour from wine red to green end point (U.S. Salinity Lab. Staff, 1954, Method 7400). Formula used was given below:

$$\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+} = \frac{(\text{Volume of EDTA used for titration (mL)} \times 0.01 \text{ N})}{(\text{Volume of soil extract (mL)})} \times 1000$$

Sodium

Sodium was determined by using flame photometer. A standard curve was drawn by using the sodium standard solutions (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 ppm) which were run on flame photometer. These were used to used to calibrate the instrument. And then Na^{+} concentration was determined in the soil was calculating with regression equation obtained by drawing the calibration curve of standard solutions (U.S. Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954; Method, 10).

Soluble anions

Determination of carbonates

For the assessment of carbonates, 5 mL soil extract was titrated with 0.01 N H_2SO_4 solution after using 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator till colourless end point (U.S. Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954; Method, 12). Carbonates (me L^{-1}) were calculated by developing the following equation:

$$\text{CO}_3^{2-} (\text{me L}^{-1}) = \frac{R_1 \times N \times 1000}{V}$$

Where

R_1 = volume of H_2SO_4 used (mL)

N = normality of acid

V = volume of soil extract (mL)

Determination of bicarbonates

After the determination of carbonates, aliquot was used for determining the bicarbonates in the same soil extract sample. Titration was done with 0.01 N sulfuric acid after adding 2 to 3 drops of methyl orange as an indicator until a yellow endpoint appeared (U.S. Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954; Method, 13).

$$\text{HCO}_3^{-1} (\text{me L}^{-1}) = \frac{(R_2 - R_1) \times 0.01 \text{ N of H}_2\text{SO}_4}{(\text{Volume of soil extract (mL)})} \times 1000$$

R_1 is the volume of H_2SO_4 used for the determination of carbonates.

R_2 is the volume of H_2SO_4 used for the determination of bicarbonates.

Determination of chlorides

Chloride was determined by utilization aliquot after carbonates and bicarbonates, titrate with 0.01 N silver nitrate until brick red endpoint in and using potassium chromate (K_2CrO_4) as indicator (Ryan et al., 2001). Chloride concentration (me L^{-1}) was determined by following formula:

$$\text{Cl}^{-1} (\text{me L}^{-1}) = \frac{(\text{Volume used of AgNO}_3 \times 0.01 \text{ N of AgNO}_3)}{(\text{Volume of soil extract (mL)})} \times 1000$$

Determination of sulphates

Sulphate ions were determined by difference method (Ryan et al., 2001) and calculated by following formula:

$$\text{TSS (me L}^{-1}) = \text{EC (dS m}^{-1}) \times 10$$

$$\text{TSS} = \text{SO}_4 + \text{CO}_3^{2+} + \text{HCO}_3^{1+} + \text{Cl}^{-1}$$

$$\text{SO}_4 = \text{TSS} - (\text{CO}_3^{2+} + \text{HCO}_3^{1+} + \text{Cl}^{-1})$$

Soil organic matter

Walkley black method was used to determine the soil organic matter (Nelson and Sommers 1982). Air dried, and ground 0.5 g of soil was weighed then 20 mL of H₂SO₄ and 10 mL of potassium dichromate was added then mixed properly and allowed to cool for 30 minutes and then, diluted to 200 mL by adding distilled water. After adding 15 drops of diphenylamine as indicator and then titrated with 0.5 N ferrous ammonium sulphate solution until dull green colour was appeared. Three blanks were also run having no soil solution.

Pre-incubation

For pre-incubation, 100 g of soil was added in incubation jars and pre-incubated for 10 days at 50% WHC and 25°C.

Treatments

After the pre-incubation of 10 days, compost of banana peels and potato peels were applied in the soil at the rate of 5 g kg⁻¹ of soil. For the comparison one control treatment was maintained. Five treatments were used in the incubation experiment: T0: Control (soil without amendment), T1: Banana peel (5 g kg⁻¹ soil), T2: Banana compost (5 g kg⁻¹ soil), T3: Potato peel (5 g kg⁻¹ soil), T4: Potato compost (5 g kg⁻¹ soil)

Incubation experiment

CO₂ released was trapped in 10 mL of 1 M NaOH solution placed in the jars. Soil moisture was maintained at 50% water holding capacity (WHC) by periodically weighing jars and adding distilled water as needed. Incubation was conducted at 20°C for 75 days. NaOH solution was replaced at scheduled intervals (1, 2, 5, 7, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75 days) to quantify CO₂-C release. The released carbon dioxide was quantified by titrating the trapped solution mixture with 0.1 M HCl solution by adding phenolphthalein as an indicator (Anderson 1982). This study quantified soil CO₂-C emissions as an indicator of soil respiration, while other greenhouse gases such as CH₄ and N₂O were not measured.

Soil microbial biomass carbon

After the completion of 75 days of incubation, microbial biomass carbon was determined by method of chloroform fumigation extraction (Vance et al., 1987). Two subsamples were taken from each replicate: one fumigated and one non-fumigated. Fumigated as well as non-fumigated samples were dissolved in 20 mL of 0.5 M K₂SO₄ solution and after shaking extracted in plastic bottle. Then, 4 mL of that extract was titrated with 0.0337 M ferrous ammonium sulphate solution in presence of 5 mL

of H₂SO₄, 1 mL of K₂Cr₂O₇ and 2-3 drops of phenanthroline indicator. Blanks were prepared using all reagents without soil. The purpose of chloroform is to kill microbes and release contents in soil solution. The difference between fumigated and non-fumigated subsamples was soil microbial biomass carbon (SMBC). Microbial biomass carbon was calculated using a conversion factor (kEC) of 0.45.

Carbon dioxide efflux

Carbon dioxide trapped in NaOH solution was measured by back titration with 0.1M HCl solution. One mL of NaOH trap solution was taken and added 6-7 drops of BaCl₂ solution then 2-3 drops of Phenolphthalein indicator pinkish colour appeared, after this titrated slowly until a colorless endpoint was reached. Three blanks of NaOH were also titrated. The CO₂-C released was quantified by back titration of NaOH with 0.1 M HCl. The total CO₂-C was calculated using:

$$\text{Total (CO}_2\text{)} = \frac{(12 \times V1 \times 0.1)}{(2 \times V2) \times (B - V3)}$$

Where:

V1 = volume of HCl used for titration (mL)

V2 = soil weight (g)

B = blank titration volume (mL)

V3 = correction for previous CO₂ trap (mL)

Soil extracellular enzymes activity

The fluorogenically labeled substrate approach was used to quantify enzymatic activity (Pritsch et al., 2004; Sanaullah et al., 2011). The substrates were dissolved in 2-methoxyethanol before being diluted with sterile water to measure enzyme activity (Hoppe 1983). Based on a preliminary optimization experiment, the saturating concentrations of fluorogenic substrates were used as follows: 200 μM for 4-MUF-β-glucopyranoside, 200 μM for 4-MUF-N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminide, 200 μM for 4-MUF-phosphate, and 100 μM for L-Leucine-7-AMC (Table 3). Enzyme assays were conducted using 50 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.5) to maintain stable reaction conditions. For enzyme assays, 1 g fresh soil was homogenized with 50 mL buffer, and 200 μL of soil suspension was transferred to microplate wells. Enzyme activity was calculated from fluorescence values using standard curves and expressed as nmol g⁻¹ soil h⁻¹. Both β-Glucosidase and chitinase enzymes were involved in the C cycle, and their relevant substrates are 4-methylumbelliferone-β-glucopyranoside and 4-methylumbelliferone-N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminide, respectively. Their function is to degrade cellulose and chitin. Acid phosphatase is an enzyme involved in the phosphorous cycle, and the substrate used for this enzyme is 4-methylumbelliferone-phosphate. Leucine aminopeptidase, an enzyme involved in the nitrogen cycle, as well as peptide degradation, and the substrate used for this enzyme, is L-Leucine-7-amido-4-methylcoumarin (AMC).

Table 3 Substrates for enzymes activity estimation and functions

Enzymes	Substrate	Functions
Carbon Cycle		
β-Glucosidase	4-MUF-β-glucopyranoside	Cellulose degradation
Chitinase	4-MUF-N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminide	Chitin degradation

Nitrogen Cycle

Leucine-aminopeptidase

L-Leucine-7-AMC

Peptides degradation

Phosphorus Cycle

Phosphatase

4-MUF-Phosphate

Phosphorous degradation

4-MUF = 4-methylumbelliferone and 7-AMC = 7-amino-4-methyl coumarin.

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) under a completely randomized design (CRD) to evaluate the effect of different kitchen waste treatments on soil CO₂-C emissions, microbial biomass carbon, dissolved organic carbon, enzyme activities, and soil aggregation. Treatments were considered as fixed effects with four replicates (n = 4). When significant treatment effects were observed, mean comparisons were performed using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test at $p \leq 0.05$. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error (SE). All statistical analyses were performed using Statistix 8.1 software.

Results

Cumulative C-CO₂ emissions with intervals

The emission of carbon dioxide at different intervals of days was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased with the addition of kitchen waste and their compost at 5 g kg⁻¹ of soil. Each treatment had greater CO₂ emissions in first 30 days of interval and then slow down but increased continually. Cumulative CO₂ emissions were highest in fresh potato peel (597 mg C kg⁻¹ soil) and lower in potato compost (542 mg C kg⁻¹ soil). Banana peel (596 mg C kg⁻¹ soil) produced higher CO₂ than banana compost (551 mg C kg⁻¹ soil), with control soil emitting the lowest CO₂ (463 mg C kg⁻¹) as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Carbon dioxide emissions from soil (mg C kg⁻¹ soil with the addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg⁻¹ soil. Time interval of incubation was 1 to 75 days and data were representing as mean \pm SE, Each treatment was replicated four times (n = 4) in a completely randomized design

Cumulative C-CO₂ emissions

The cumulative CO₂ emissions were significantly higher in all kitchen waste treatments compared with the control; however, compost treatments produced lower emissions than the corresponding fresh peel treatments. Cumulative CO₂ emissions were highest in fresh banana and potato peels (~597 mg C kg⁻¹ soil), lower in their composted forms (542–551 mg C kg⁻¹), and lowest in control (463 mg C kg⁻¹). These observations are specific to the controlled incubation system shown in Fig. 2. Although compost treatments reduced CO₂ emissions compared with fresh peels of the same feedstock, all organic amendments resulted in higher CO₂ emissions than the control treatment.

Fig. 2 Cumulative CO₂ emissions (mg C kg⁻¹ soil) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg⁻¹ soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean ± SE (n = 4). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at p ≤ 0.05.

Microbial biomass carbon

Microbial biomass C significantly increased (p ≤ 0.05) with the application of kitchen waste treatments and their compost at rate of 5 g kg⁻¹ of soil. MBC increased with all amendments, with banana compost highest (1055.7 mg C kg⁻¹) and banana peel lowest among amended soils (765.8 mg C kg⁻¹). Notably, the control (885 mg C kg⁻¹) exceeded banana peel, likely due to rapid decomposition and microbial turnover in fresh banana peel during early incubation.

Fig. 3 Soil microbial biomass C (mg C kg^{-1} soil) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg^{-1} soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean \pm SE ($n = 4$). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Soil dissolved organic carbon

Dissolved organic C was significant ($p < 0.05$) affected with addition of banana peel and compost. DOC was highest in banana peel (148 mg C kg^{-1} soil), followed by potato compost (101 mg C kg^{-1} soil), with banana and potato composts showing lower values ($31\text{--}32 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil). Control exhibited the lowest DOC ($26.5 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil) as shown in the Fig. 4. The increasing trend of treatments was observed as banana peel ($148.84 \pm 11.87 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil) > potato peel ($101.51 \pm 4.53 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil) > potato compost ($32.27 \pm 2.10 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil) > banana compost ($31.10 \pm 2.53 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil) > control ($26.54 \pm 2.53 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ soil).

Fig. 4. Dissolved organic C (mg kg^{-1} soil) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg^{-1} soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean

\pm SE (n = 4). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

β -glucosidase enzyme activity

β -glucosidase enzyme activity was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased by the application of banana compost ($994.58 \pm 58.62 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) as compared to banana peel ($644.55 \pm 39.86 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$). But in the case of potato, β -glucosidase enzyme activity was significantly increased by potato peel application ($411.62 \pm 34.10 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) as compared to potato compost ($371.73 \pm 12.82 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) as shown in the Fig. 5. The increasing trend of applied treatments is given as banana compost ($994.58 \pm 58.62 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > banana peels ($644.55 \pm 39.86 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > potato peels ($411.62 \pm 34.10 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > control ($371.73 \pm 12.82 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > potato compost ($336.36 \pm 32.47 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$).

Fig.5 β -glucosidase enzyme activity ($\text{nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg^{-1} soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean \pm SE (n = 4). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Chitinase enzyme activity

Chitinase enzyme activity was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased by the application of potato compost ($32.86 \pm 1.97 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) as compared with potato peel ($16.55 \pm 1.148 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) as shown in the Fig. 6. Similarly, banana peels ($19.96 \pm 1.52 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) showed maximum chitinase enzyme activity by comparing with banana compost ($18.57 \pm 1.80 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$). The increasing trend of applied treatments given as potato compost ($32.87 \pm 1.97 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > banana peels ($19.96 \pm 1.52 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > banana compost ($18.57 \pm 1.80 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > potato peels ($16.55 \pm 1.148 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > control ($16.12 \pm 0.86 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$).

Fig. 6 Chitinase enzyme activity ($\text{nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg^{-1} soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean \pm SE ($n = 4$). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Phosphatase enzyme activity

Phosphatase enzyme activity was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased by the application of banana compost ($809.97 \pm 37.76 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) as compared to banana peel ($776.73 \pm 64.23 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$). Similarly, the compost of potato ($677.51 \pm 62.10 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) increased the phosphatase enzyme activity by comparing with potato peel ($654.45 \pm 25.52 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) as shown in the Fig. 7. The increasing trend of applied treatments given as banana compost ($809.97 \pm 37.76 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) > banana peels ($776.73 \pm 64.23 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) > potato compost ($677.51 \pm 62.10 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) > potato peels ($654.45 \pm 25.52 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) > control ($600.81 \pm 57.15 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$).

Fig. 7 Phosphatase enzyme activity ($\text{nM g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg^{-1} soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean \pm SE ($n = 4$). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among

treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Leucine aminopeptidase enzyme activity

Leucine aminopeptidase enzyme activity was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased with the addition of banana peel ($191.21 \pm 3.42 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) while the banana compost ($181.86 \pm 3.25 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) showed minimum leucine aminopeptidase enzyme activity. Similarly, potato peel ($168.68 \pm 4.43 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) increased the Leucine aminopeptidase enzyme activity as compared potato compost ($159.01 \pm 2.16 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) that showed minimum activity as shown in the Fig. 8. The increasing trend of applied treatments given as banana peels ($191.21 \pm 3.42 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > control ($186.98 \pm 5.72 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > banana compost ($181.86 \pm 3.25 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > potato peels ($168.68 \pm 4.43 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) > potato compost ($159.01 \pm 2.16 \text{ nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$).

Fig. 8 Leucine aminopeptidase enzyme activity ($\text{nM g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) with addition of potato and banana peels and compost at 5 g kg^{-1} soil. Incubation duration was 75 days and data represent mean \pm SE ($n = 4$). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Soil macroaggregates

Soil macroaggregates ($>250 \mu\text{m}$) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by the addition of organic kitchen waste at the rate of 5 g kg^{-1} of soil (Fig. 9.). It was observed that banana peel ($81.83 \pm 1.86\%$) showed maximum soil macroaggregates while banana compost ($71.57 \pm 1.98\%$) showed minimum percentage of macroaggregates. The potato peel ($79.54 \pm 1.41\%$) increased the soil macroaggregates by comparing with potato compost ($75.10 \pm 2.07\%$). The increasing trend of applied treatments given as banana peels ($81.83 \pm 1.86\%$) > potato peel ($79.54 \pm 1.41\%$) > potato compost ($75.10 \pm 2.07\%$) > banana compost ($71.57 \pm 1.98\%$) > control ($61.43 \pm 5.99\%$).

Fig. 9 Impact of banana and potato compost and peels on soil macroaggregate fractionation (%). Macroaggregate fractionation was done at the end of 75 day of incubation study. Data represent mean \pm SE (n = 4). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Soil microaggregates

Soil mesoaggregates (53-250 μm) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased by the addition banana compost (12.72 \pm 0.84%) as compared with banana peel (10.23 \pm 0.85%) as shown in the Fig. 10. Potato compost (11.39 \pm 1.04%) showed maximum percentage of mesoaggregates while the potato peel (10.23 \pm 0.85%). The increasing trend of applied treatments given as control (14.23 \pm 0.46%) > banana compost (12.72 \pm 0.84%) > potato compost (11.39 \pm 1.04%) > banana peel (10.23 \pm 0.85%) > potato peel (9.40 \pm 1.05%).

Fig. 10 Impact of banana and potato compost and peels on soil mesoaggregate fractionation (%). Mesosoaggregate fractionation was done at the end of 75 day of

incubation study. Data represent mean \pm SE (n = 4). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Soil microaggregates

Soil microaggregates ($< 53 \mu\text{m}$) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased by the addition of banana compost ($15.26 \pm 1.24\%$) showed maximum soil microaggregates as compared with banana peel ($7.48 \pm 0.74\%$). Similarly, the potato compost ($15.14 \pm 1.14\%$) increased the soil microaggregates by comparing with the potato peel ($10.71 \pm 0.76\%$) showed minimum percentage of soil microaggregates (Fig. 11). The increasing trend of applied treatments given as control ($18.40 \pm 0.90\%$) > banana compost ($15.26 \pm 1.24\%$) > potato compost ($15.14 \pm 1.14\%$) > potato peel ($10.71 \pm 0.76\%$) > banana peel ($7.48 \pm 0.74\%$).

Fig. 11 Impact of banana and potato compost and peels on soil microaggregate fractionation (%). Microaggregate fractionation was done at the end of 75 day of incubation study. Data represent mean \pm SE (n = 4). Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Discussion

The experiment was conducted to evaluate the effects of banana and potato peels and their composts on soil respiration, microbial biomass carbon, dissolved organic carbon, enzyme activities, and soil aggregate fractions during the incubation period. This study evaluated the effects of banana and potato peels and their composts on soil carbon dynamics, microbial activity, enzyme responses, and aggregate distribution during incubation. The higher CO_2 emissions under potato peel amendment indicate rapid mineralization of easily decomposable carbon fractions, suggesting that fresh residues provide a more immediate substrate for microbial respiration than stabilized compost materials. The sustained CO_2 release in banana peel-amended soil further supports the role of labile organic compounds in driving prolonged microbial respiration during incubation. Furthermore, Higher CO_2 emissions observed in potato peel treatments may indicate greater availability of easily decomposable organic

substrates for microbial activity during incubation, which may stimulate microbial respiration and lead to increased CO₂ release during decomposition (Shakeel et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020). The higher CO₂ emissions observed in peel treatments compared with compost treatments may be attributed to the presence of more readily decomposable organic substrates. This interpretation is supported by the higher dissolved organic carbon observed in peel-amended soils, which likely provided an immediate carbon source for microbial respiration. The observed increase in soil respiration aligns with previous incubation studies demonstrating that labile carbon inputs enhance microbial activity and CO₂ release, particularly during early decomposition phases (Sajjad et al., 2025; Ofosu et al., 2021). Compared with previous studies on organic amendments, the stronger respiratory response in peel treatments highlights the importance of substrate quality, particularly C:N ratio and biochemical composition, in regulating decomposition rates. These findings demonstrate that the form of organic input governs carbon turnover dynamics, where fresh residues accelerate short-term mineralization while composted materials contribute to more stabilized carbon pools (Liang et al., 2017). The higher microbial biomass carbon under compost treatments suggests that stabilized organic matter supports sustained microbial growth, whereas fresh residues may favor rapid respiration over biomass accumulation as shown in Fig. 3. It was reported that the waste of plant materials input to the soil that promote soil microbial populations and their activities, resulting in relatively faster decomposition of organic matter (Wang et al., 2015). The elevated dissolved organic carbon in peel-amended soils indicates a greater availability of labile carbon fractions, which likely stimulated microbial respiration and enzymatic activity during early decomposition stages. Dissolved organic carbon is considered an important indicator of readily available carbon sources for soil microorganisms (Wichern et al., 2020). Extracellular enzyme activities such as β -glucosidase, chitinase, phosphatase, and leucine aminopeptidase were influenced by the application of banana and potato peels and their composts. Soil aggregate fractions including macroaggregates (>250 μm), mesoaggregates (53–250 μm), and microaggregates (<53 μm) were influenced by the addition of kitchen organic waste at 5 g kg⁻¹ soil. Banana peel resulted in the highest proportion of macroaggregates, while potato peel also exceeded potato compost, indicating that fresh residues contributed more effectively to macroaggregate formation than composted materials. Similarly, banana compost increased mesoaggregate and microaggregate fractions compared with banana peel treatments. The variation in aggregate fractions suggests that both fresh and composted residues influence soil structure differently, with fresh inputs promoting macroaggregate formation through transient binding agents, while compost contributes to longer-term stabilization. Banana compost increased the β -glucosidase enzyme activity as compared to peels of banana. Similarly for the enzymatic activity of chitinase increased by the application of potato compost peel of potato and banana. Phosphatase enzyme activity was improved by banana compost as compared to banana peels. Leucine aminopeptidase activity was highest in banana peel-amended soil, likely reflecting enhanced nitrogen mineralization from proteinaceous substrates in fresh residues, as supported by soil enzyme studies on organic amendments (Zhu et al., 2019). The differential enzyme responses indicate substrate-specific microbial functioning, where compost amendments enhanced β -glucosidase, chitinase, and phosphatase activities due to stabilized organic substrates, whereas fresh residues stimulated enzymes associated with rapid nutrient cycling. Compost treatments generally enhanced β -glucosidase, chitinase, and phosphatase activities, whereas leucine

aminopeptidase activity was higher in peel-amended soils compared with compost treatments. Increased β -glucosidase activity with compost addition may reflect enhanced microbial activity associated with the decomposition of organic substrates (Wu et al., 2013). Soil macro ($>250\ \mu\text{m}$), meso ($53\text{--}250\ \mu\text{m}$) and micro ($<53\ \mu\text{m}$) aggregates fractionates were affected by the addition of kitchen organic waste at the rate of $5\ \text{g kg}^{-1}$ of soil. It was observed that potato compost showed maximum soil macroaggregates compared by potato peel that showed minimum percentage of soil macroaggregates. Banana compost resulted in the highest proportion of mesoaggregates, whereas banana peel treatments showed comparatively lower mesoaggregate percentages. Similarly for soil microaggregates were increased by the application of banana compost while the banana peel showed minimum percentage of soil microaggregates. Changes in soil macro ($>250\ \mu\text{m}$), meso ($53\text{--}250\ \mu\text{m}$), and micro ($<53\ \mu\text{m}$) aggregates following organic residue addition indicate that organic amendments can influence soil structural stability during incubation (Li et al., 2016). This study evaluated only $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$ emissions during soil respiration; therefore, the findings cannot be extended to other greenhouse gases such as CH_4 or N_2O .

Future Perspectives

Future research should advance beyond controlled soil incubation studies toward a One Health framework, integrating soil, plant, animal, and human health systems. The transformation of kitchen waste into compost not only influences soil carbon dynamics but also has downstream implications for food safety, nutrition, and public health, forming a continuous soil–food–health nexus .

At the agricultural level, emerging biotechnological tools such as CRISPR-based genome editing offer opportunities to design crop varieties with enhanced nutrient use efficiency and stress tolerance under organic amendment systems (Jabeen et al., 2025; Fatima et al., 2026). These innovations can be aligned with compost-based soil management to improve resilience against climate-induced stresses such as drought, thereby strengthening sustainable crop production systems.

From a microbiological and food systems perspective, the role of beneficial microbes should be further explored across the soil–food continuum. For example, the application of microbial technologies in food fermentation systems (Ahmed et al., 2024) and soil microbial enhancement strategies suggests a shared functional basis that can be optimized for both soil fertility and human nutrition. However, this must be balanced with food safety concerns, as contamination risks in raw food systems remain significant (Riaz et al., 2026), highlighting the need for integrated safety frameworks.

Nutritional and metabolic health dimensions also intersect with sustainable soil management. Functional foods, including probiotic-based dietary interventions (Rashid et al., 2026), plant-derived bioactive compounds, and nutrient-enriched formulations (Butt et al., 2025a; Butt et al., 2025b), depend fundamentally on soil quality and nutrient cycling. Furthermore, micronutrient dynamics such as zinc-mediated metabolic regulation (Butt et al., 2026a) and epigenetic modulation through diet (Butt et al., 2026b) indicate that soil-driven nutrient availability can have long-term physiological and genetic implications in humans.

Animal health models further reinforce this connection. Studies on hepatotoxicity mitigation through dietary interventions (Khan et al., 2024) and biosafety evaluation of novel protein systems (Butt et al., 2025a) suggest that agricultural inputs ultimately influence animal health and food chain safety. Similarly, comparative analyses of meat and plant-based analogues (Butt et al., 2025c) emphasize the importance of

sustainable agricultural inputs in shaping future protein systems.

Beyond biological systems, technological and socio-economic integration will be critical. Artificial intelligence tools can enhance precision agriculture, waste management optimization, and sustainability education (Kamal et al., 2026), while broader sustainability frameworks must incorporate social dimensions of environmental performance (Khurshid et al., 2026). These aspects are essential for scaling compost-based solutions within real-world agricultural systems.

Human health outcomes, including musculoskeletal adaptations (Mahmood et al., 2026) and dental health interventions (Jabeen et al., 2026b), may seem distantly related but reinforce the broader concept that environmental quality, nutrition, and health systems are deeply interconnected under the One Health paradigm.

Finally, future studies should prioritize long-term, field-scale assessments, incorporating multiple greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O), soil carbon sequestration, and ecosystem resilience. Integrating composting strategies with circular bioeconomy models and sustainable food systems can provide a pathway toward climate-smart agriculture while simultaneously improving human and environmental health outcomes.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that banana and potato peels and their composts differentially influenced soil carbon dynamics, microbial activity, enzyme responses, and aggregation during incubation. Compost amendments showed greater potential for improving soil biological activity and structural stability compared with fresh residues under controlled conditions. Fresh peels resulted in higher CO₂-C emissions, indicating rapid mineralization of labile organic carbon. Compost amendments enhanced microbial biomass, enzyme activities, and soil structural stability compared with fresh residues. Organic amendments influenced soil aggregation, with compost treatments contributing to improved structural stability compared with fresh residues. These findings highlight the role of composted organic amendments in enhancing soil biological functioning and structural quality under incubation conditions. As only CO₂-C emissions were measured, conclusions are limited to soil respiration and cannot be extended to overall greenhouse gas mitigation. Fresh residues increased CO₂ release during incubation due to rapid decomposition of labile carbon fractions. Compost application also improved soil aggregation and microbial functioning, indicating its potential for sustainable organic waste recycling and soil health improvement. However, the study quantified only CO₂-C emissions associated with soil respiration; therefore, conclusions are limited to this component of the carbon cycle.

Statements & Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

"Not applicable".

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Availability of data and materials

Raw CO₂-C, enzyme, microbial biomass, and aggregate data will be shared upon reasonable request or provided as supplementary material

Authors' contributions

MN- Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; AN – Conceptualization, Formal Analysis; AI – Investigation; AW – Data Curation; KW – Formal Analysis, Review & Editing; MS – Conceptualization, Formal Analysis; UG – Investigation; MS – Formal Analysis, Investigation; AR - Methodology; MMH - Review and Editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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